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A STUDY ON CONSTRUCTION AND STANDARDIZATION OF FRUSTRATION INVENTORY FOR THE SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Construction means to prepare the inventory statements. All the items to be used in the process of standardizing must be constructed. It naturally leads one to take items through the process of pilot administration and analysis. In the present study, the term construction indicates especially the construction of a Frustration Inventory. Frustration is a situation of obstacles or hindrance in required satisfaction or goal-oriented behavior. Sometimes a tense mental condition or habitual behavior originated due to obstacle or hindrance is also called Frustration. For this study, it means the Frustration obtained on the basis of scores on inventory constructed to study through various factors. For the present research, an inventory has been constructed by constructing and properly arranging items keeping in mind various factors to find out frustration among the school students. Mainly there are two hindrances found behind the origin of frustration. They are external or environmental hindrances and internal or individual operant. The external hindrances include physical, economic and cultural hindrances whereas the internal hindrances include body limitations, mental limitations, and mental struggles. The main objectives of the study are to measure the level of the Frustration of Secondary Schools students. This paper tries to investigate on Construction and Standardization of Frustration Inventory for the Secondary School students from different schools of West Bengal. Here, the researcher had decided to construct and standardize the frustration inventory for the secondary school students of West Bengal State. Therefore, students of standard-9th and standard-10th of secondary schools of West Bengal State (Bengali Medium) became the population of the present study. The total sample comprises of 400 students were randomly selected from different Bengali medium schools and equally distributed among boys and girls students. The following tools were used to for the collecting the data of the present study i.e., Frustration Inventory prepared by Dr. Pallaviben Patel & Verbal and Non-Verbal Intelligence Test prepared by Dr. K.G. Desai and published by Institute of Psychological and Educational Research and Guidance. The obtained data were analyzed with the help of Mean Median, Mode, Standard Deviation, 't'-test and coefficient of correlation. The finding of the present study shows that the proportion of frustration in boys and girls was found to be equal. The study also indicates that area creates an effect on frustration. The proportion of frustration was found to be equal among the students of Standard-9 and Standard-10. The proportion of frustration in rural girls was found to be higher than that of the boys. The proportion of frustration of boys and girls of the urban area was found to be equal. The proportion of frustration in rural boys was found to be higher than that of the urban boys. Whereas the researcher also found that the proportion of frustration in urban girls was higher than that of the rural girls.

Keywords: Construction, Standardization, Frustration Inventory, External or Environmental hindrances, Internal hindrances, Proportion, Secondary School Students

INTRODUCTION:

Education is a very effective process of facilitating learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits. Education is a word we hear very familiar in everyday life because it is an important activity undertaken by almost all rang of society. Education is a conscious and deliberate effort to create an atmosphere of learning and the learning process so that learners are actively developing the potential for him to have the spiritual strength of religious, self-control, personality, creativity, intelligence, noble character, and the skills needed themselves and society.

Frustration is a kind of negative emotion stimulated upon encountering a barrier to satisfying one's wants, goals or expectations, which disrupts the ongoing action. Frustration means the feeling of being upset or annoyed as a result of being unable to change or achieve something. It is the feeling that accompanies an experience of being thwarted in attaining one's goal. The term 'frustration' also indicates a deep chronic sense of insecurity and dissatisfaction arising from unresolved problems or unfulfilled needs; it is a feeling of anger or annoyance caused by being unable to do something. In psychology, frustration is a common emotional response to the opposition, related to anger, annoyance, and disappointment, frustration arises from the perceived resistance to the fulfillment of an individual's will or goal and is likely to increase when a will or goal is denied or blocked. There are multiple ways individuals cope with frustration such as passive-aggressive behavior, anger, or violence, although frustration may also propel positive processes via enhanced effort and strive. Frustration originates from feelings of uncertainty and insecurity which stems from a sense of inability to fulfill needs. If the needs of an individual are blocked, uneasiness and frustration are more likely to occur. When these needs are constantly ignored or unsatisfied, anger, depression, loss of self-confidence, annoyance, aggression, and sometimes violence are likely to follow. In psychological terms, frustration is a general emotional retort to antagonism. In a relationship with anger and displeasure, it occurs from the apparent resistance to the accomplishment of individual will. The greater the hindrance and the superior the will, the more the frustration is expected to occur in some one's mind. For this study, it means the Frustration obtained on the basis of scores on inventory constructed to study through various factors. It means a questionnaire or inventory to examine opinions, attitudes, and

responses. It is not like an objective test but it dependent on subjectivity which gives the opposite response. For this study, an inventory has been constructed by constructing and properly arranging items keeping in mind various factors to find out frustration among the students. Mainly there are two hindrances found behind the origin of frustration. They are external or environmental hindrances and internal or individual operant. The external hindrances include physical, economic and cultural hindrances whereas the internal hindrances include body limitations, mental limitations, and mental struggles. Due to this resistances keeping in mind the frustration originated in an individual and the main effects of the frustration,

several statements have been constructed for frustration inventory. Thus, the present study has been conducted by the researcher to identify not only the problems of Indian youths but also the secondary school students of Paschim Medinipur District of West Bengal as they face innumerable problems leading to Frustration.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE:

Gilmar (1966), defined, frustration as, “the state of an organism resulting when the satisfaction of motivated behaviour is made difficult or impossible when the goal is blocked.”

Continuous frustration of our basic needs may lead to serious maladjustments or condition of mental ill-health (**Kuppuswamy, 1969**). Frustration is a kind of negative emotion stimulated upon encountering a barrier to satisfying one's wants, goals or expectations, which disrupts the ongoing action. In a study of **Dragomir and Greculescu (2011)** frustration tolerance was compared between criminal adolescent and non-criminal adolescent. A significant difference was found among criminal and non-criminal adolescent. The criminal adolescents' frustration tolerance was significantly lower in comparison with non-criminal adolescents. **Dave (2013)** found no gender difference in frustration of students of Secondary schools in his investigation on Construction and tryouts of Frustration Inventory. It means that gender does not create an effect on frustration. It was also found that males and females are significantly different in their reaction to frustration (**Bhutia, 2014**).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The main objectives of the study were the following:-

- To construct and standardize the Frustration Inventory.
- To measure the level of the Frustration of Secondary Schools students.
- To examine the Frustration of Secondary Schools Students in relation to their Standard.
- To investigate the Frustration of Secondary Schools Students in relation to their gender.
- To assess the Frustration of Secondary Schools Students in relation to their area of residence.

HYPOTHESES:

Considering the objectives of the study following hypothesis were framed by the investigator-

- **Ho1:** There would be no significant difference between the mean scores of Frustration of Standard-9th and Standard-10th students.

- **Ho2:** There would be no significant difference between the mean scores of Frustration of Boys and Girls students.
- **Ho3:** There would be no significant difference between the mean scores of Frustration of Urban area and Rural area students.
- **Ho4:** There would be no significant difference between the mean scores of Frustration of Boys and Girls students of Standard-9th.
- **Ho5:** There would be no significant difference between the mean scores of Frustration of Boys and Girls students of Standard-10th.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

The scope of the present study is limited to only some selected area of West Bengal State. This study was conducted for the Secondary Schools students of Bengali medium. The sample was collected from W.B.B.S.E. Board affiliated Schools of Paschim Medinipur district only. The study is limited to only ten West Bengal Board Schools.

POPULATION & SAMPLE OF THE STUDY:

The students of standard-9th and standard-10th of secondary schools of West Bengal State (Bengali Medium) became the population of the present study. The sample for the present study was selected randomly. Students of standard-9th and standard-10th were selected using a cluster sampling technique, from each school. Thus, schools were selected through random sampling method and the students from those selected school were selected using cluster sampling method.

No attempt has been made to maintain the equal ratio of standard-9th and standard-10th, boys & girls and rural & urban area students. Final sample with reference to the standard, gender, and area described in the following table.

Standard	Gender	Boys		Girls		Grand Total
	Area	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	
Standard-9 th		45	40	46	60	191
Standard-10 th		52	48	55	54	209
Total		97	88	101	114	400
		185		215		

VARIABLES OF THE STUDY:**• INDEPENDENT VARIABLES-**

1. Standard
2. Gender: Boys & Girls
3. Area of Residence
4. Board: W.B.B.S.E.

• DEPENDENT VARIABLE-

1. Frustration

TOOLS OF THE STUDY:

➤ The following tool was used for collecting the data of the present study.

- The Frustration inventory. This tool was prepared and standardized by the researcher.
- Frustration Inventory prepared by Dr. Pallaviben Patel.
- Verbal and Non-Verbal Intelligence Test prepared by Dr. K.G. Desai and published by Institute of Psychological and Educational Research and Guidance.

RELIABILITY & VALIDITY OF THE TEST:

The reliability of the Frustration Inventory on the basis of the split-half method it was found r_{tt} Reliability Coefficient = 0.95, 0.96 & 0.90 and test-retest method it was r_{tt} Reliability Coefficient = 0.82 and in Cronbach Alpha Method it was found to be r_{tt} Reliability Coefficient = 0.94. The validity of the scale was assessed by finding the coefficient of correlation and it was found to be 0.79 in Inventory prepared by Dr. Pallaviben Patel & 0.72 in Inventory prepared by Dr. K.G. Desai.

METHOD OF THE STUDY & DATA COLLECTION:

Looking into nature of the present research study i.e. construct and standardize frustration inventory for Secondary school students to measure their frustration, Descriptive Survey Method was selected since the research was dealt with the data collection and analysis for measurement of frustration. The researcher gave sufficient time to the students for filling up the questionnaire. The data regarding the Frustration Inventory of the students were collected from the students by visiting the selected Schools.

DATA ANALYSIS:

After the collection of data from the selected sample, the scoring is done, and then the raw score is converted into standard scores. Keeping in view the objectives as well as the design of the study, the coefficient of correlation and 't' test were used for the analysis of the data. Collected Data gathered were classified according to variables and frequency distributions were also prepared for different groups. Based on the frequency distribution of each group, statistical measurements as below were carried out.

- Mean Median, Mode, Standard Deviation and coefficient of correlation.
- The significance of the difference of means between groups
- Verification of normal distribution of the scores
- Establishing the norms, based on the significance of the difference of means of the scores, determining their PR and T- scores.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS:

- **Ho1:-** There would be no significant difference between the mean scores of Frustration of Standard-9th and Standard-10th students.

Where, $p > 0.05$

The calculated t-value is less than Table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. On the basis of the result, the Null hypothesis is accepted. So, it can be concluded that there will be no significant difference found between the mean scores of Frustration of Standard-9th and Standard-10th students. Thus, students of standard-9th and standard-10th were found to have equal in frustration which shows that standard is not affecting variable to frustration.

- **Ho2:-** There would be no significant difference between the mean scores of Frustration of Boys and Girls students.

Where, $p < 0.05$

The calculated t-value is higher than Table value 2.58 at 0.05 level of significance. On the basis of the result, the Null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, it can be said that the significant difference found between mean scores of boys and girls of secondary schools. Hence, by comparing mean scores, girls were found to have higher frustration than boys which shows that the gender of students is affecting variable to frustration.

- **Ho3:-** There would be no significant difference between the mean scores of Frustration of Urban area and Rural area students.

Thus, the Effect of the area was found on Frustration. So, it can be concluded that Students of the rural area were found to have higher than students of an urban area as far as frustration concern.

- **Ho4:-** There would be no significant difference between the mean scores of Frustration of Boys and Girls students of Standard-9th.

Where, $p < 0.05$

The calculated t-value is higher than Table value 2.58 at 0.05 level of significance. On the basis of the result, the Null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, it can be said that the significant difference found between mean scores of boys and girls of standard-9th. Hence, by comparing mean scores, girls of standard-9th were found to have higher frustration than boys of Standard-9th which shows that the gender of standard-9th students is affecting variable to frustration.

- **Ho5:-** There would be no significant difference between the mean scores of Frustration of Boys and Girls students of Standard-10th.

Where, $p > 0.05$

The calculated t-value is less than Table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. On the basis of the result, the Null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, it can be said that no significant difference found between mean scores of boys and girls of Standard-10th. So, boys and girls of Standard-10th were found to have equal in frustration which shows that the gender of Standard-10th students is not affecting variable to frustration.

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

- Approx 20.17% of students were from the whole sample were found to be under “**less than normal frustration level**” or “**low level of frustration**”.
- Approx 21.00% of students were from the whole sample, were found to be under “**normal frustration level**” or “**medium level of frustration**”.
- Approx 19.96% of students were from the whole sample were found to be under “**more than normal frustration level**” or “**high level of frustration**”.
- Approx 18.70% of students were from the whole sample were found to be under “**extreme frustration level**”.
- It is clear that the majority of the students in the sample were found to have a medium level of frustration. Majority Percentage of the students was found to have approximately equaled on a high level and low-level Frustration.
- The effect of gender was not found on the frustration of students of secondary schools. It means that gender does not create an effect on frustration. So that proportion of frustration in boys and girls was found to be equal.

- The effect of the area was found on the frustration of secondary school students in which the proportion of frustration was found to be more among students of a rural area than the students of urban areas. Thus, it can be said that the area creates an effect on frustration.
- There was no effect of standard of study on the frustration of secondary school students. Thus, the standard of study does not create any effect on frustration. The proportion of frustration was found to be equal among the students of Standard-9 and Standard-10.
- There was a significant effect of gender on the frustration of secondary schools students of rural areas. The proportion of frustration in rural girls was found to be higher than that of the boys.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATION OF THE STUDY:

1. The tool of frustration inventory made available by this study to measure frustration in secondary school students can become useful to researchers desiring to conduct researches in this field.
2. This study can be useful for teachers in taking appropriate steps to know and remove the proportion of frustration in students with the help of this frustration inventory.
3. This study can be useful to know and remove the types of frustration lies in the students.
4. With the help of this inventory, the teacher will be able to take appropriate steps to know and remove frustration in the students.
5. Hidden frustration in secondary schools students will be found out and can be measured.

CONCLUSION:

Frustration is the state of some desire or tendency being unfulfilled. Evidently, frustration is the outcome of an obstacle in the part of an individual's goal or objective. From this study, the investigator has identified that there are significant differences among secondary school students' frustration with regard to gender & locality. For better mental health and lower frustration, the students should imbibe some moral values and hobbies. Defense Mechanism is also a process which one can use to react to frustration. When some students get frustrated, they turn into tension and ill-tempered behavior. They experience a perturbed feeling in their appetite and also show a variety of other reactions of frustration. So need of the time is to make people aware of the effects that frustration and this reaction mechanism is putting on our minds. A healthy mind resides in healthy body emphasis should be laid on to intricate values healthy activities in such school so that the adolescents can never delineate or alienate towards the wrong side. Moreover, the parents, teachers, counselors and the society at large should work together to improve the mental health and lower the frustration scores of the school students.

REFERENCES:

- **De Botton, Alain (April 2011).** *The Consolations of Philosophy.* New York: Vintage Books, a division of Random House Inc. p. 80. ISBN: 0-679-77917-5.
- **Dollard, J., Doob, L., Miller, N., Mowrer, O. and Sears, Rn. (1999).** *Frustration and Aggression.* New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- **Gardner, Murphv (1999).** *An Introduction to Psychology.* Basic Books, New York.
- **Kapoor, A., Burluson, W., and Picard, R.W. (2007).** *Automatic prediction of frustration.* International Journal of Human-Computer Studies, 65, 724-736.
- **Mahon, N.E., Yarchesk,i A., Yarcheski, T.J., and Hanks, M.M. (2007).** *Relations of low frustration tolerance beliefs with stress, depression, and anxiety in young adolescents.* Psychological Reports, 100(1), 98–100.
- **Mandler, G. (1975).** *Mind and Emotion.* New York: Wiley.
- **Miller, NE (July 1941).** *The frustration-aggression hypothesis.* Psychological Review, 48 (4): 337–342, doi:10.1037/h0055861.
- **Vyas, A. (2002).** *A Study of Learning Style, Mental Ability, Academic Performance and other Ecological Correlates of Undergraduate Adolescent girls of Rajasthan.* Ph.D. Thesis in Education, Meerut: Ch. Charan Singh University.
- **Zhang, Q. (2006).** *An Exploration of Frustration Education for Adolescence and Counter measures.* Ethnic Educational Study, 17(5), 11-15.

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